

Role of Chhattisgarh Tourism Board in Development of Chhattisgarh Tourism Industry

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ABSTRACT: Tourism is recognized as a major service industry governed by the laws of supply and demand. Tourism is one of the important economic contributors of GDP and employment generation. Chhattisgarh Tourism Board is playing an important role in development and improvement of tourism destinations. The focus is also on tourism policy made by CTB. All program, policies and work show that it is done in effective manner.

KEYWORDS: Development, Economy, policy, role, tourism.

INTRODUCTION

India is a country popularly known for its culture, tradition and heritage across all over the world is also known for its tourism destinations. Country offers a lot of various types of tourism products to its tourists. Tourism is one of the important economic contributors of GDP and employment generation. Tourism industry of Chhattisgarh state contributes very less to its economy. The Ministry of tourism creates plans and policies for the development of tourism industry and its promotion in all over the world. Similarly at state level in Chhattisgarh, Chhattisgarh Tourism Board (CTB) is playing an important role in development and improvement of tourism destinations.

DEFINITION OF TOURISM

According to WTO (1993) "Tourism encompasses the activities of persons traveling and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business, and other purposes."

According to Mathieson and Wall. "The temporary movement of people to destinations outside their normal places of work and residence, the activities undertaken during their stay in those destinations, and the facilities created to cater to their needs."

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

- I. To study the role and importance of CTB.
- II. To know the various types of tourists destinations in Chhattisgarh.
- III. The focus is also on tourism policy made by CTB.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is a descriptive study, based on secondary data. Data collection was done through books, brochures and various internet websites.

CHHATTISGARH STATE AND ITS HISTORY.

Up till year 2000 Chhattisgarh was a part of Madhya Pradesh state on 1st November 2000, 16 southern-eastern districts were separated and a separate state namely Chhattisgarh was formed as Raipur its capital. At present state consists of 32 districts sharing its boundaries with Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh, Orissa, Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Jharkhand and Telangana. The newly formed state is famous for its heritage, tribal culture, handicrafts, culture, and tradition and is blessed with various natural resources. Some of the famous tourism destinations are Chandrasasini Devi Temple, Mahamaya Temple Ratanpur, Bambleshwari Temple, Danteshwari Temple, Chitrakot Waterfall, Kailash Kutumsar Caves, Boramdeo Temple, Sirpur Heritage Site, Balrampur Hot Spring, Gadiya Mountain, Teerathgarh Falls, Bhuteshwar Shivaling, Ghatarani Waterfall Temple, and Mainpat Hill Station. Other than that there are 3 national parks and 11 wildlife sanctuaries.

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Formation of Chhattisgarh Tourism Board

Chhattisgarh Tourism Board was constituted by the state government on 18 November 2002 for the implementation of tourism activities in the state of Chhattisgarh. As a result of the division of Madhya Pradesh Tourism Development Corporation under the Madhya Pradesh State Reorganization Act, services of 50 officers and employees to the Government of Chhattisgarh. The space was taken and possession of movable and immovable assets within the limits of the state of Chhattisgarh by 21 November 2002, by the Chhattisgarh Tourism in physical forms Madhya Pradesh State Tourism Development Corporation. Chhattisgarh Tourism Board has constituted 18 member governing board for the last 15 years, every effort is being made by Chhattisgarh Tourism Board for tourism development and tourism activities in the state at national and international level.

OBJECTIVES OF CHHATTISGARH TOURISM BOARD

The Chhattisgarh Tourism Board's goal is to promote tourism on a global scale. The Chhattisgarh Tourism Board was formed to promote the state as a whole and to create Chhattisgarh as a major tourist destination by creating tourism infrastructure throughout the state with the help of the government, the local community, and the business sector.

- I. To promote and advertise numerous tourist destinations in Chhattisgarh both domestically and internationally.
- II. To improve infrastructure throughout the state in order to provide basic tourism services.
- III. To develop tourist information centre at different destinations.
- IV. To improve the quality and appeal of Chhattisgarh's tourism experience.
- V. Protect and promote the state's prosperity as well as its diverse cultural heritage.
- VI. Increase tourism's contribution to economic development and associated fields.
- VII. To encourage private investors to invest in tourism infrastructure development, to promote tourism in the state of Chhattisgarh, and to ignite the attention of persons and organizations involved in tourism related activities
- VIII. Dissemination of information about tourism potential. For the purpose of inviting domestic and foreign travel agents, tourism promotion agencies and travel writers travel bloggers in the state of Chhattisgarh.
- IX. Organizing seminars, workshops, exhibition studies, classes tours in India and abroad, and through publication of book magazine Travel periodicals Travel Guide and through brochures and advertisements, To take action to promote tourism With the aim of promoting tourism, organizing national, state level cultural, social and such other festivals and assisting in side by side from the events.
- X. Implement such other works and schemes as may be entrusted to the tourism board by the state government.

TOURISM POLICY

The tourism policy of Chhattisgarh is focused on establishing a unique image of the state and developing it as an attractive tourist destination. Some specific efforts have been outlined by the state to fulfill this objective, such as infrastructure and institutional development, tourism product supply, marketing etc. The main objective of this policy is to facilitate the role of the government and to respect the intellectual property and rights of the local community. While implementing the tourism policy, the state will encourage only those efforts which lead to sustainable development of the tourism sector and maintain the balance of the environment. In addition, the State Government shall encourage the participation of the local communities and ensure their participation in the protection and promotion of the rich cultural heritage of the State. To achieve these objectives, the state will pass suitable laws and establish the State Tourism Development Board as the nodal agency for the development of tourism sector and implementation of tourism policy.

MAIN OBJECTIVES OF TOURISM POLICY

- I. To encourage sustainable tourism in the state from economic, cultural and ecological point of view.
- II. To strengthen the quality and attractiveness of tourism experience in Chhattisgarh.
- III. To preserve, promote and propagate the rich and diverse cultural heritage of the State.
- IV. To encourage the efforts of private investors in the development of tourism related infrastructure.
- V. To encourage new concepts in the field of tourism such as time share, eco tourism, rural tourism, adventure tourism etc.
- VI. To respect the intellectual property and rights of the local community. In order to fulfill the above objectives, some specific efforts have been highlighted by the State, which are classified as follows:
- VII. Infrastructure and Institutional Development.
- VIII. Supply and marketing of tourism products.

KEY POINTS OF TOURISM POLICY

- I. Infrastructure and Institutional Development.
- II. Incentive to private sector.
- III. Improvement of road network of tourism centers for infrastructure and human resource development.

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- IV. Empowerment of Institutional Structures.
- V. Improvement in supply of tourism products

(A). **Eco-tourism:** Primary attraction centers like wildlife areas, camping sites, and trekking facilities will be developed. Sonmuda (Marwahi), Mainpat (Surguja), Keshkal Valley (Kanker), Chaiturgarh (Korba), Garden (Jashpur), Kotumsar Cave, Kailash Cave, Tirathgarh Waterfall, Chitrakot Waterfall (Bastar) and Kanger Valley National Park, Barnawapara. Sitanadi, Udanti, Achanakmar sanctuaries will be developed as natural tourist destinations. Apart from the above, emphasis will be laid on development of herbal gardens and yoga for natural health, Ayurveda resorts etc. to promote eco-tourism development in the state by taking advantage of abundance of medicinal plants.

(b). **Cultural, Ethnic & Rural Tourism** - To show the valuable heritage of the state, the sites and villages near the heritage property like old palaces, havelis and enclosures will be identified and developed as tourist centers. These will be coordinated in the eco-tourism path of the state and focused for tourism development in the entire state. Under this, arts and crafts products will also be included so that local rural employment can be promoted. The State Government will ensure that the archaeological heritage is maintained and managed in a proper and commercial manner. Bhoramdev, Rajim, Sirpur, Tala, Malhar and Shivrinarayan will be developed mainly as heritage heritage. Various cultural fairs and festivals will be organized from time to time for the cultural development of the state. Local festivals like Dasara of Bastar, Madai of Narayanpur etc. will also be encouraged.

(c)**Adventure Tourism:** Adventure tourism like trekking, rock climbing, sailing, parasailing, water sports, water rafting, parasailing, water sports etc. will be developed in the state. The state government will make arrangements for training of youths / girls for the development of adventure tourism activities so that adventure tourism can be developed at these commercial level in the state. Gangrel Dam, Madamsilli Dam, Kodar Dam will be developed for adventure sports.

(d) **Pilgrimage tourism:** For the growth of pilgrimage tourism in the state, Dharamshala and other pilgrimage destinations will be created. Buddhist pilgrims will be able to visit the state's Buddhist tourism sites, which will be linked to the greater Buddhist circle. From the perspective of national and international pilgrimage, Rajim, Champaran, Chandrahasini Devi, Dongargarh, Shivrinarayan, Giroudpuri, Dantewada, Ratanpur, Sirpur, and Mainpat will be developed. • Tourism that is both commercial and recreational Construction of business-cum-recreation centers and theme parks, which will give required amenities to traders, will be promoted for the growth of business-cum-recreational tourism in the state. This will result in the growth of business tourism. The building of state-of-the-art conference centers, lecture halls, and other venues for corporate gatherings will be promoted. Hotels, theme parks, multiplex theatres, health spas, retail malls, golf courses, and other amenities will be built to meet the needs of corporate travelers with high purchasing power.

EFFECTIVE MARKETING

Development Work during year 2020

1. Under the "Prasad Yojna" of the Government of India, Ministry of Tourism, Rs. 4333.07 lakh has been sanctioned. The construction work is being started under the project.
2. A project of Rs. 96.10 crore is being conducted under the Swadesh Darshan Scheme of the Ministry of Tourism, Government of India. Jashpur, Kunkuri, Mainpat, Kamleshwarpur, Maheshpur, Kurdar, Saroddadar, Gangrel, Kondagaon Nathianwagaon, Jagdalpur, Chitrakot, and Tirathgarh are all part of this tourism circuit. Kurdar Eco Tourist Resort, Kondagaon Ethnic Tourist Resort Saroda Dadar Ethnic Tourist Village, and Jashpur Ethnic Tourist Resort, Kunkuri, Marg Suvidha at Maheshpur, Nathianwagaon from Chief Minister's house E-launched this year on 14.08.2020 and 01.11.2020, respectively.
3. The amount of the second installment to Collector Dhamtari for putting up a home stay, camping material, and solar plant in village Jabarra, district Dhamtari was issued, and Rs. 19.09 lakh was sanctioned in the second phase for the promotion of eco-tourism.
4. Sonakhan has been added to the state's list of designated tourist destinations as a historical and natural tourism destination in the Balodabazar-Bhatapara district.

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS

I. Year 2018-2019:-

1. Best Emerging Destination Zee Business Travel awards 2018
2. Best Heritage Destination-Domestic Travel Leisure-Indian Awards 2018
3. Best Tribal Tourism Destination Global Star Awards 2018

II. Year 2019-2020

1. Publication of information related to Chhattisgarh tourism in the annual souvenir published by the Indian Forest Service.
2. Publication of information related to Chhattisgarh Tourism for Coffee Table Book of Indian Railway (West Zone).

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3. Workshop under Festival of Wellbeing organized in Raipur on 12 June 2019 for the promotion of International Yoga Day under the joint aegis of India Tourism, Mumbai and Chhattisgarh Tourism Board.
4. Yoga was promoted by India Tourism, Mumbai on 20th June 2019 at Bardiha Lake - View Tourist Cottage, Gangrel, District Dhamtari and on 1st June 2019 at Hotel Johar Chhattisgarh Raipur through Yoga practice camp.

Conclusions

Over all study concludes that Chhattisgarh Tourism Board is playing a vital role in development, promotion of state's tourism. All program, policies and work shows that work is done in effective manner. Above achievements prove that the Chhattisgarh tourism is being popularizing.

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